

MODERN ECO-ARCHITECTURAL TECHNIQUES IN THE DESIGN OF PHYSICAL CULTURE AND LEISURE COMPLEXES OF UKRAINE

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***Abstract.** The article analyses the main methods and principles of green building, and gives the main conditions for the successful design of "green" buildings. "Green" architecture is a current construction trend, one of the elements of ecological approach in architecture, providing an inseparable connection of modern buildings with the environment. The world experience of designing sports centres in Germany and Austria has been studied. The trend of combining natural elements and architecture is shown to be relevant. Landscape design of areas allows you to create a visual continuity between the building and the surrounding area. "Green" roofs also refer to the world standard for the construction of sports complexes (France). An analysis of international "green" sports facilities projects has shown that the development of this trend is based on the principles of combining natural components with architectural shaping. The necessity of introducing certification of sport facilities according to "green" standards is shown. Certification is a natural extension of the design process, as the requirements of an environmental standard are based on the principles and approaches of the sustainable development concept.*

The aim of this study is to introduce elements of international "green" building standards in the design of a sports and recreation facility in Ukraine (Lyski, Odessa region). The project has highlighted and detailed two priority areas - green roofing

and landscaping of the surrounding area. Around the building is a spacious park with plants and trees that go up in stages (lawn, bushes, deciduous and coniferous trees). Their use will provide noise reduction and have a positive effect on the psycho-emotional state of visitors. The park space is planned with the use of small architectural forms and serves as a place to walk and relax. A "green" roof or roof garden construction will provide passive energy saving through thermal insulation properties, oxygen production, air humidity control, and neutralisation of dust and harmful gases in the surrounding space. The project aims to improve the environmental situation in the project area, creating an interesting and environmentally friendly architectural object.

Keywords: *"green" architecture, ecological problem, eco-system, greening, "green" roof, yoga centre.*

Introduction. The international architectural industry already has strict standards and certifications for buildings and structures. Many environmental certification standards have emerged (LEED; BREEAM, WEL. Fitwel and others), which implement the principles of eco-architecture. The main feature of ecological architecture is love and respect for nature. This concept in architecture, also known as "green" architecture, reduces the impact of the building on the environment and ecosystem.

The environmental problem has become the most urgent one in everyone's sphere of life these days. Mankind has become aware of the need to conserve natural resources and environmental problems. Global urbanisation has led to new sources of environmental transformation and pollution. There is a need to find effective solutions to existing problems. For this it is not enough just to green the area, it is also important to develop architecture using modern trends in design, i.e. "green architecture". Eco-architecture can be one way of solving a whole range of environmental problems.

The economic benefits of operating green buildings lie on the surface: reduced

energy consumption leads to lower energy bills; reduced water consumption reduces the cost of water supply; the introduction of green building principles shapes public opinion and promotes the popularity and return on leased space; "green" buildings that are certified can receive tax breaks and subsidies; the high comfort levels of green buildings contribute to the health of their occupants [1].

Among the global trends in green building are the increasing attention and interest in the creation of artificial eco-systems that could mimic the properties, processes and design of ecological systems in nature, including the creation of autonomous energy-efficient buildings.

The purpose of the study. Implementation of the world experience of "green" construction in the project of a sports and recreation facility.

Green components in shaping the eco-environment.

In the modern world, the issue of environmental ecology and human health is increasingly being raised. Urban growth, a large number of enterprises and human activity are destroying nature with its many landscapes and vegetation.

A physically developed body is good and beautiful, but it is not a guarantee of health and longevity. Speaking about the positive role of physical development, we should not forget about the state of mind: it is mental balance and inner harmony that affect health and contribute to longevity. From a medical point of view, the key to health and longevity lies in endorphins - the hormones of joy: serotonin and melatonin. The production of these hormones, in turn, depends on the mood with which a person perceives the world around them. It is the natural environment that surrounds a person that has the most favorable impact. It helps people to relax, restore physical strength, enrich their spiritual world, and improve their health.

Scientific studies show that unity with nature helps to reduce anxiety, relieve stress and even lower high blood pressure. Contemplation of the beauty of nature stimulates vitality and calms the nervous system, providing positive emotions. This

state is achieved by the aesthetic expressiveness of the landscape. A person gains peace, tranquility, mental balance, and thus recovery [2].

Greening is not only aesthetic, but also has a positive effect on the urban environment. Through photosynthesis, plants produce oxygen and also have the property of clearing the air of dust and gases, reducing their concentrations. The total area of green spaces in cities should occupy more than half of its territory.

Many scientists have explored the interaction of architecture and nature in their work. The definition of "green architecture" has not yet reached a theoretical generalisation. The questions of the methods and principles of Green Architecture have not yet been fully addressed in scientific and theoretical works.

Modern architects and designers use methods of incorporating natural elements in architecture. These include: Renzo Piano, Friedensreich Hundertwasser, Andri Putman, Ralph Hancock, Jean-François Dorès [3], Patrick Blank, Stanley Hart White and others. In their projects they used different ways of vertical gardening and green roofs. However, there have been people passionate about and exploring the idea of growing 'living' structures with the implementation of this in their projects (Axel Erlandson, Peter Cook, John Krubsack, Ferdinand Ludwig [4], Arthur Wichula, Giuliano Mauri, Alessandro Rocca, Joachim Mitchell and others) implement the idea of growing "living" structures (Fig. 1).

A special feature of Green Architecture is the introduction of plants - living material. Therefore it is always in a state of "movement" - growing and developing, always changing through the cycle of seasons, temperature, light. Plant architecture is a good vector for biovariety as well. Plant walls, terraces, green roofs have a great influence on the effect of biological passageways to be created in the city.

Studying the experience of Green Architecture and using its current trends is relevant and timely both globally and in Ukraine. Historical architecture and urban planning in Ukraine used to exist in harmony with nature, as evidenced by the large areas of green spaces in the country. But modern trends of intensive urban

development over parks and green areas lead to the fact that nature is gradually disappearing from the cities.

Fig. 1. Natural elements in eco-architecture

The challenge of developing Green Architecture for design and construction consists of finding the right place for plants (as living material) among buildings that will be located in the most efficient living conditions and will be useful and beautiful for the environment, creating a harmonious relationship with the architectural structures.

The use of natural components in the formation of architecture can vary depending on the volumetric-spatial, functional, and constructive task (interiors, courtyards, roofs, building facades, balconies, terraces, galleries, loggias, individual buildings and objects, small architectural forms, landscape aeration, etc.) All these methods of using natural elements improve the aesthetic, psychological, planning, functional, energy-efficient and structural qualities of the building and its plots. They

reduce noise levels, affect temperature, refresh the volume, have a positive effect on people, improve mood, and serve as natural insulation.

The objects of the study were examples of "green" buildings for sports and leisure centres in global experience. These architectural projects use different principles of "Green Architecture".

First and foremost, Green Architecture is the art of shaping space by means of the natural landscape. Greenery is the main building material for such creativity. With the right planning, plants can become the material for most building elements instead of those that people build with metal and concrete.

"Green architecture integrates the natural landscape into architecture by using natural components to create forms, uniting architecture with nature. Thus, nature, which is being displaced from urban areas, can be returned to the interior or exterior space of buildings and structures or created from natural materials. [5]

One such example is the Kaltensteinhalle project, a wooden gym in Germany (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Kaltensteinhalle gym project, Germany, 2021

The new gym was designed as a compact, functional and very economical structure made of wooden elements. Only the parts in contact with the ground are made of reinforced concrete. The design takes advantage of the terrain to place functional blocks on several levels. Most of the hall is built into the slope. The elegant appearance of the building continues in the materials: the wooden supporting structure remains visible, the interior of the hall is decorated with simple and durable

wooden elements.

Landscaping is an important component of an effective building design. Landscape elements can provide buildings with benefits such as shielding them from the sun, protecting them from the wind, contributing to passive cooling, and creating opportunities for natural ventilation. In addition, landscape elements can be useful for purifying air and water, absorbing floodwater, improving aesthetics, providing recreational amenities, and developing ecological habitats for wildlife [6]. For example, the FSF sports and entertainment center in Austria (Fig. 3).

Green roofs are an important component in ensuring the sustainability of holistic development in construction. In addition to their economic role, they also play an important environmental role. The benefits of roof greening fall into three main categories: rainwater control, energy saving (thermal insulation, reduced energy consumption) and providing an environmentally friendly urban environment.

Fig. 3. FSF sports and entertainment center, Austria, 2021

Adherence to installation technologies is a key component of the success of

such a project. It is necessary to correctly summarize the weight of all the layers (insulation, drainage, soil, and plant), as landscaping creates an additional load on the supporting structure of the roof and the entire building and it is important to take this into account so that the plants do not destroy the roof [7].

Roof greening has become a global standard, mandatory for the construction of buildings in a number of countries. Ukrainian cities continue to be actively built up, so it is only a matter of time before this type of greening is introduced into state building codes, but the sooner this decision is made, the sooner Ukraine will be able to adopt the experience of other countries and prevent our cities from turning into "stone jungles."

At this point in time, rooftop greening is popular all over the world and there are many fascinating examples of this architectural solution. One of these examples is the presented project of a sports complex located in Montjoie Park, in the center of Saint-Cyr-sur-Loire (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Sports complex at a primary school and kindergarten for students, France, 2019

The architects sought to design a building that combines architecture and landscape, creating a sense of visual continuity between the landscape park and the building. When viewed from the entrance to the park, the massiveness emphasizes

the horizontal layout. Landscaping plays an important role in the appearance and layout of the building. It is an integral part of the design, making its presence visible everywhere. The "green roof" creates a sense of continuity with the park, the playground is interspersed with grassy banks that descend from windows throughout the building; and the kindergarten's rooftop educational garden with insect corner and vegetable beds is an ideal place to learn about nature. The main building is surrounded by two playgrounds: a sports ground and a children's playground, which overlook the park.

Research object: a project of a yoga center in Lisky village (Odesa region, Ukraine).

Purpose of the study: to consider the main features of green architecture in modern construction using examples of experience in designing green facilities; to show that eco-friendly architectural solutions make it possible to improve the environment and create an interesting and attractive architectural object.

Research methods: The study used general scientific methods - studying literature sources, conducting theoretical analysis, comparing, systematizing, and generalizing theoretical observations on modern trends in green architecture.

RESULTS

Based on the results of the research, a project of a yoga center in the village of Lisky, Odesa region, with a developed greening system was developed (Fig. 5). The building is being designed in the relatively young but actively developing Limansky district of Odesa region on the border with Suvorovsky.

The building was designed in a mixed Modern and Bionic style. These styles are characterized by the laconicism of the image, maximum functionality, the absence of a large amount of decor, a harmonious combination of space and form, and the most advantageous combination of glass and concrete.

The project development includes measures aimed at protecting the environment from pollution, preserving the fertile soil layer and atmospheric air. The

project envisages the use of energy-saving, environmentally friendly materials and structures.

Fig. 5. General plan of the yoga center project and photo of the project site (Lisky village)

The aim of the project is to create a comfortable space for people who are passionate about yoga and other spiritual practices. Lecture halls and study rooms have been designed for sharing experiences and holding mass events (Fig. 6).

The use of large halls for group yoga classes, meditations and other practices is also envisaged. The projected building is designed for sports activities for people of all age groups, from young children to the elderly.

Fig. 6. Layout of the yoga centre and structural cross-section of the building

This is aided by an attractive façade and a location that is quiet and away from the noise of the city. The grounds include a spacious park with a promenade around the lake.

The voluminous structural façade panels, made in the form of a repeating flower of life pattern, have a sacred meaning, which is also aimed at attracting the club's target audience.

The use of specific elements of green architecture will create an environment that can improve psychological comfort and the ecological situation in the projected area.

Two priority areas were identified and elaborated in the project: the development of a green roof and landscaping of the adjacent territory. The spaces are planned with the use of small architectural forms and green spaces: a natural pond, benches with decorative planters, tree plantings, trimmed shrubs, and a lawn. The spaces are planned to be arranged as a zone for combining yoga and recreation (Fig. 7).

A spacious park with gradually rising landscaping (lawn, shrubs, deciduous and coniferous trees) has been designed around the building, which reduces noise levels, has a positive effect on people, improves mood, and serves as a place for walking and relaxation.

In addition, many woody shrubs and flowering plants release phytoncides into the air. They enhance the body's immunological reactions and tissue regeneration processes, which is important for visitors to sports centres [8].

High-tech solutions that increase comfort levels, longevity of structures and meet a number of environmental requirements of 'green' standards include the greening of the "fifth facade", or the construction of rooftop gardens.

Fig. 7. Perspective images of the yoga center project (Lisky village)

The project envisages the installation of a green roof, which will provide passive energy saving, expressed in the significant thermal insulation properties of the green roof for the building (preventing roof heating and retaining heat in the

building). Environmental benefits of a green roof: generation of additional oxygen, regulation of humidity, neutralisation of dust and harmful gases in the surrounding space, accumulation of rainwater.

Practical advantages of green roofs:

- Green roofs are far more durable than conventional roofs if the technology is followed, as the multi-layered "cake" of modern materials with a "glaze" of plants serves as the best waterproofing and thermal insulation for the rooms underneath. The service life of a green roof is extended by the service life of the roof by a factor of 2-3;

- a flat green roof becomes a useful area and can, depending on the type of greening, be used for a wide variety of purposes as a compensation for the lack of greenery in the city [9].

CONCLUSIONS

"Green architecture" seeks to reduce the negative impact of buildings on nature and ensure only a positive impact on the lives of current and next generations.

The definition of "Green architecture" has long gone beyond just landscape design. The study of experience in the design and construction of modern "green" objects leads to the following conclusions: the design of "green architecture" is a new stage in the development of modern architecture, based on the principles of connecting natural components with architectural shaping.

Methods of "green" roofing and landscaping of the adjacent territory are used in the design of the yoga centre (Ukraine, Lisky). The project aims to create an environment that can increase psychological comfort and the environmental situation in the projected area with the application of elements of "green architecture".

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